

THE HURRICANE-PROD CAST: A TERRESTRIAL MECANOGLYPH FROM THE MIDDLE PONTIAN OF THE DACIAN BASIN (SLĂNICUL DE BUZĂU VALLEY, ROMANIA)

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Abstract. We present an unusual impact trace of hurricane-prod cast type, which has been possibly generated by the very strong atmospheric winds, produced, in the northern part of the Dacian Basin, during the latest Miocene, *i.e.* Pontian times. The above-mentioned hypothesis is based on the presence of the planimetric details, along with the reconstruction of the transported body and the existence of the undulations made by the impact shock.

Key words: paleowinds, terrestrial mecano-glyph, Early Pliocene, Portaferrian, Eastern Carpathian Foredeep.

1. INTRODUCTION

The oldest researches focused on "hieroglyphs" dated in Romania starting with the first decades of the 20th Century (Protescu, 1912; Mrazec, 1927). Subsequently, the mecano-glyphs from the Cretaceous-Paleogene flysch sediments of the Romanian Carpathians were used to solve various issues, such as: **a)** the establishment of the bed position (Noth & Krejci-Graf, 1929; Pătruț, 1955; Grigoraș, 1955; Băncilă, 1958; Popescu, 1958); **b)** the determination of the source areas and paleocurrent directions (Dimian & Dimian, 1962; Contescu *et al.*, 1963; Dimitriu, 1964; Dumitriu & Dumitriu, 1965; Panin & Mihăilescu, 1967; Contescu *et al.*, 1968; Jipa *et al.*, 1973); **c)** the identification of the syndromic mecano-glyphs of a secondary origin in the Transcarpathian Flysch zone (Jipa & Mihăilescu, 1973). The mecano-glyphs of the Miocene molasse deposits have been previously studied by Paucă (1952), Panin (1961, 1964), Dimian & Dimian (1962) and Polonic & Polonic (1968), while those from the Eastern Carpathian Foreland were investigated by Macarovici *et al.* (1967), Jipa (2006) and Jipa & Olariu (2009).

Among the various structures of the mecano-glyph type from flysch and molasse sediments, a distinct category is represented by vectorial erosion structures, generated by objects that have been transported by water currents. Based on the investigations of Dźułyński & Walton (1965), Anastasiu & Jipa (1983) and Dźułyński (1996), the imprints of the current transportation objects may be grouped into continuous ones, such as dredging marks, including groove marks and chevron marks, and discontinuous, comprising impact and rolling marks, which are represented by prod marks, bounce marks, brush marks, saltation marks and roll marks. Usually, the prod marks have longitudinal striations and a sharp or a round apex, being quite small, that is 10-15 cm in length and up to 1 cm in depth (Dźułyński & Walton, 1965; Anastasiu & Jipa, 1983). Additionally, some of these mecano-glyphs may have sharp margins, due to the cut of the object stuck in the sediment; other mecano-glyphs are very elongated, short or large, features that indicate the impact of the surface with an object fallen under a big angle (Dźułyński & Walton, 1965). As directional structures, the tool marks and the scour marks represent the key for understanding the paleogeography of various sedimentary basins (Dźułyński, 1996; p. 102).

This paper presents the first occurrence of a new type of prod mark, within the Middle Pontian (Portaferrian) sediments from the Carpathian Foreland; some paleoenvironmental considerations are also advanced herein.

2. GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The region where the new mecanoglyph has been observed is situated in the Neogene Dacian Basin (**Fig. 1a**), being placed in the Slănicul de Buzău Valley, on the Sârbești locality territory, in the area of Buzău Land Geopark (**Fig. 1c**). The Middle Pontian deposits, cropping out at Sârbești, are situated on the western flank of the Berca-Arbănași anticline (e.g., Macarovici, 1961; Jipa & Olariu, 2009), being characterized, from a paleoenvironmental point of view, by the occurrence of alternating continental and brackish up to marine facies. The continental sediments are fluvial ones, belonging to the alluvial channel paleoambiances and to those placed outside the channel. Lithologically, the former ones contain unstratified clays related to a flood paleoplain, fine-grained sands, showing flood sheets, coal and coaly clays and paleosoils. The brackish-marine sedimentation encloses stratified grey clays and sandstones showing symmetrical ripple marks. The aforementioned deposits were interpreted (Jipa & Olariu, 2009) as accumulated in a deltaic plain. Within this paleoambiance, the deltaic/fluvial channels have frequently migrated laterally, allowing the accumulation of the marine sediments in a side space temporary placed outside the fluvial influence.

Recently, the lithostratigraphy and the paleoichnologic content of a Middle Pontian (Portaferrian) succession from the Slănicul de Buzău Valley was interpreted (Brustur & Jipa, 2009) as follows: the presence of the sandy sandstones with numerous rhizolithes is linked to a paleosoil, probably situated at the edge of the sedimentary basin, supporting the influence of the hydrostatic level oscillations. The presence of this pedological turbation mirrored the colonization of the marginal lacustrine paleoenvironment with grassy vegetation and bushes, within a time of a local and/or regional regression. The continental episode, marked by a significant discontinuity surface at the Middle Pontian level, is followed by a marine transgression. This assumed sea level fluctuation is shown by the occurrence of an indurated sandy sequence, containing a numerous population of *Gastrochaenolites* (Brustur & Jipa, 2009). The above-mentioned ichnogenus is often associated with the erosional exhumation of sediments, previously buried, being typically linked to rapid sea level modifications (Carmona *et al.*, 2007).

3. RESULTS

The prod mark has been identified on the fined-grained sandstone bed, 15-20 cm in thickness, on a surface of around 0.85 m², cropping out in the Slănicul de Buzău Valley (**Fig. 1c**). In the field, a sector of around 0.35 m² that contains the prod mark has been noticed (**Fig. 1d**). Taking into account the dimension, the weak rolling, along with its occurrence in the

Slănicul de Buzău River bed, it is possible that this rock fragment comes from the top of the lower part of the Middle Pontian (Portaferrian) stage, as indicated in the stratigraphical column (**Fig. 1b**) illustrated in Jipa & Olariu (2009). In **Fig. 2** the planimetric details of the prod mark are shown (**Fig. 2a**), as well as the reconstruction of the aerial transported conic body (**Fig. 2b**).

The mold of the sedimentary structure related to the object impact shows, on the pelitic bed, the presence of a semiconical depression, ending with a sharp apex. Flattened lobes, with different lengths, are placed perpendicularly on the depression axis, at various distances. These lobes mark the bilateral expulsion of the mud, after the initial impact of the wind transported object (**Fig. 2a**). The lobes are disposed on different angles, *i.e.* between 55° and 85°, in relation to the depression axis; some of them have thickened terminations, illustrative for the mud overcrowding, at their distal end (**Fig. 2a, X**). The occurrence of these lobes with various shapes, dimensions and orientations, linked to the depression created after the object impact, is indicative for the synchronism of their formation with the depression, *i.e.* a syndepositional process. This genetic approach excludes the possibility that the prod mark was superposed on current ripple marks, as it may be interpreted, at first glance (**Fig. 1d**).

The mold of the impact depression shows several morphological particularities, allowing for a hypothetical reconstruction of the transported object (**Fig. 2b**): **a**) the tronconic shape, around 30 cm long and with a sharp edge; **b**) the presence of straight longitudinal striations or slightly curved, placed towards the base; **c**) the aspect of deformed body, probably due to the extremely powerful wind and materialized by apparently torsion portions (**Fig. 2b, X; Fig. 3**); **d**) the sharp contact between the depression and the host rock (**Fig. 2b, XX**); **e**) the presence, in front of the depression, of parabolic undulations produced by the impact shock (**Fig. 2a, XXX**).

4. DISCUSSION

In the Dacian Basin (Eastern Paratethys domain), the Pontian stage covers ca. 1 Ma. This stage corresponds, globally, to the upper part of the Messinian and the lower part of the Zanclean, including the Miocene/Pliocene boundary (Rădan & Rădan, 1998; Vasiliev *et al.*, 2004; Snel *et al.*, 2006).

During the Middle Pontian (= the Portaferrian substage), the Dacian Basin was supplied with clastic material from four active source areas, two of them in the intra-Carpathian regions and the other two in extra-Carpathian areas (Jipa & Olariu, 2009). The occurrence of the proximal sedimentary successions, as a transition between the marine sedimentation and the continental one (Jipa *et al.*, 2006), including fresh water mollusks (e.g., *Potamoscaptha*) from the base of the Portaferrian (Macalet, 1997), signaled by various authors (Jipa & Olariu, 2009; Stoica *et al.*, 2012; Floroiu *et al.*, 2013), shows a significant regression, possibly linked to the

Fig. 1. **a.** Location of the studied Middle Pontian deposits at Sârbești, in the Dacian Basin, Romania (after Jipa & Olariu, 2009); **b.** The stratigraphical column of the Middle Pontian sediments with the position of the sequences characterized by ripple marks and fluvial channels (modified after Jipa & Olariu, 2009); **c.** The outcrop exposed in the Slănicul de Buzău Valley, at Sârbești; **d.** Detail of the sandstone bed containing the hurricane-prod cast (photo Titus Brustur, November 2012). The red star indicates the position of the sandstone bed with the impact mark from **b** and **c**.

Fig. 2. Hurricane prod-cast **a.** Planimetric detail of the prod mark (drawing after the picture). Interrupted thick yellow lines mark the approximated contour of the sharp edge body (“XX”) transported by the wind and the lateral lobes, perpendicularly disposed on the stick mark axis. The distal part of the lobes marked “X” represents the mold of the mud ejected after the impact; the undulations of the shock wave are noted “XXX”. **b.** Reconstruction of the body transported by the wind, with the impression of the longitudinal striations (“XX”) and of the deformed parts of the semiconsolidated material (“X”). **c.** Schematic section of the impact trace (not at scale; the arrows indicate the direction of mud lobe movement).

Fig. 3. The mold of the impact depression; note the longitudinal striations, the aspect of deformed material with torsion parts and mud lobes, perpendicularly disposed on the depression axis.

Messinian Salinity Crisis that produced a substantial sea level drop in the Mediterranean (Bache *et al.*, 2012). Some authors (Suc *et al.*, 2011) believe that this event triggered by the tectonics in the Mediterranean has also influenced the regime of the Eastern Paratethyan realm, leading to the opening of the Iron Gates and the partial desiccation of the Dacian Basin, by a pronounced fluvial drainage; yet, this issue is under debate, as several different hypotheses have been advanced.

In our opinion, a Late Miocene paleosetting, with extended sectors with variable extension in which frequent thunderstorms took place, allowed the generation of a prod mark related to high winds. Such type of mark is for the first time described herein and we define it as “the hurricane-prod cast”. The generation of this mecanoglyph type is illustrated in **Fig. 4**. We have selected the term “hurricane” to designate the high energy aerial transport (*sensu* Marcinowski & Radwanski, 2009), characteristic of the wind speeds and intensities in hurricanes and tornadoes range.

It is known that, at present, the hurricane and tornadoe wind speed may be as high as 152 km/h up to 250 km/h (Saffir-Simpson scale), and between 40 km/h and 300 km/h (Fujita scale), respectively. Some hurricanes have reached 322 km/h, and the tornadoes 483 km/h, with devastating effects.

In some cases, crossing the land, the hurricanes may be accompanied by vortices that sometimes produce a strong suction and take over heavy objects (Lăzărescu, 1980) or even peel the asphalt (Vesilind & Carsten, 2004).

We assume that the existence of some extreme meteorological events, as aforementioned, had generated, by suction, prod marks. Probably, this kind of mark has been made by the fragments released from the semiconsolidated pelitic sediment in a shallow small basin (**Fig. 4a**) or by a part of the mud cracks (**Fig. 4b**), followed by a wind small-distance transport and impact under a small angle of the body on the surface of a semiconsolidated clay, in another small basin (**Fig. 4c**). Previously, the perturbation of the lacustrine semiconsolidated sediments, at depths between 7 cm and 25 cm, was noticed in Florida (USA), following the crossing of the *Frances*, *Jeanne* and *Wilma* hurricanes (Jin *et al.*, 2011).

The planimetric details, as well as the reconstruction of the transported body and the undulation existence made by the impact shock (**Fig. 2**) argue for a *scenario* similar to that above described. The argument of the existence of an aerial transport in the genesis of such kind of mecanoglyph is the prevailing, in the pre-Quaternary, of a climate similar to the present one; the climate simulations of the Pliocene times indicate a pronounced global warming, accompanied by the intensification of the atmospheric and oceanic circulation, along with the highest speed of the western-oriented winds (Poulsen, 2009).

Fig. 4. Model of the impact trace of the hurricane prod-cast due to the dislocation, by a strong wind, of a semiconsolidated sediment from a shallow basin (a) or parts of the mud cracks surfaces (b); the transport in the atmosphere followed by the object impact in basins filled with mud, simultaneous with the bilateral expulsion of the mud, perpendicularly on the axis of the impact depression (c).

The tropical hurricane events and the thunderstorms were considered (Duke, 1985) the main cause of the appearance of the crossed stratification *hummocky*-type in at least 107 occurrences within the Proterozoic - Recent time interval; the distribution of such sedimentological structures shows that 73 % of them have been generated by the tropical hurricanes and 27 % are due to the intense winds, related to the thunderstorms produced at low latitudes. Additionally, Duke (1985) identified *hummocky* structures in the lacustrine sediments, linked to the occurrence of the high thunderstorms.

In the Dacian Basin of the Romanian Carpathians outer part, *hummocky* structures are present in the Upper Miocene sediments, *i.e.*, during the Maeotian and Pontian Paratethyan stages (Jipa *et al.*, 2006; Jipa & Olariu, 2009). Moreover, the existence of the strong winds during the Dacian (Early Pliocene) stage, argued by the presence of the aeolian sands, was used (Filipescu, 1940) to explain the thickening of the shells belonging to the mollusk *Prosodacna* and *Viviparus* taxa. This could be caused by the high disturbance of the Pliocene lake waters from the NE part of the Dacian Basin.

We exclude the origination of the above-mentioned mecanoglyph by rheoplasia, a mechanism described by Poll *et*

al. (1981) and Plint *et al.* (1983) for explaining the presence of such structures in the Paleozoic continental sandstones from Canada. Therefore, we consider that the genetic model, as explained above, is plausible enough, including the rheologic behavior of the semiconsolidated sediment fragment, taken over and transported in the atmosphere by a strong wind similar to the nowadays hurricane.

However, a short distance transport may conserve the initial state of the pelitic material. Similarly, the initial state of the pelitic material, as the detached clay fragments that have been pushed by bottom currents, may generate longitudinal striations of the brush marks. This kind of traces was described in the Oligocene turbidites of the Polish Carpathians (Dzułyński, 1996).

The continuation of the sedimentological investigations, focused on the study of the inner structures and current mecanoglyphs (including those presented herein), may bring important information on the paleowinds orientation in the Dacian Basin during the Late Miocene times. Recently, De Vleeschouwer *et al.* (2015) noted the importance of the study of the ripple marks orientation in the reconstruction of the Middle Devonian paleowinds in the Orcadian Basin (Scotland), confirming the numerical paleoclimatic models.

5. CONCLUSIONS

a) The Miocene and Pliocene marine and lacustrine deposits of the Eastern Carpathian Foreland preserve numerous inner structures and directional mecnoglyphs of various types and origins (e.g., Jipa *et al.*, 2006; Jipa & Olariu, 2009).

b) The Middle Pontian (Portaferrian) that corresponds to the upper part of the global Messinian stage has recorded some paleoenvironmental events; one of these is the discontinuity surface marked by a regression (argued by the presence of paleosoils with *rhizolithe*), followed by a transgression, i.e. a marine sequence with *Gastrochenolithes* (Brustur & Jipa, 2009).

c) The presence of the inner structures, *hummocky*-type, in the Maeotian and Pontian sediments (Jipa *et al.*, 2006; Jipa & Olariu, 2009), along with an impact trace of hurricane prod-cast type are possibly linked to the existence, in some areas of the Dacian Basin, in those times, of extreme meteorological phenomena, such as cyclones and tornadoes.

d) The study of oscillation orientation showed by the ripple marks and the hurricane prod-casts may indicate the directions of the Miocene-Pliocene paleowinds in the Dacian Basin, helping to carry out a more comprehensive picture of the climate evolution in the Eastern Paratethyan realm.

e) The presence, in the inner part of the Eastern Carpathian Foreland, of the upper Miocene and Pliocene de-

posits, showing lithological similarities with the turbidites as in the Milcov Formation, together with inner structures and mecnoglyphs of currents (Macarovici *et al.*, 1967; Jipa, 2006) need detailed and systematic sedimentological investigations, in order to possibly identify the continuation of the orogen facies (*sensu* Paucă, 1952) in the Focșani-Pralea region.

f) The hurricane prod-casts have not been described, up to now, in any paper focused on sedimentary structures, neither in the foreign geological literature, (e.g., Pettijohn & Potter, 1964; Dźułyński & Walton, 1965; Dźułyński, 1996; Dźułyński, 2001), nor in the Romanian one (e.g., Pauliuc, 1962; Dimian & Dimian, 1962; Contescu *et al.*, 1963; Panin & Mihăilescu, 1967; Contescu *et al.*, 1968).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I gratefully acknowledge the thoughtful input by Dr. Dan Jipa, Corresponding Member of the Romanian Academy. Thanks go to Dr. Mihaela Melinte-Dobrinescu and to Dr. Sorin-Corneliu Rădan, for their helpful suggestions. The research leading to this paper has received funding from EEA Financial Mecanism 2009-2014, under the *Project "Applied research for sustainable development and economic growth following the principles of geoconservation: Supporting the Buzău Land UNESCO Geopark initiative"* (Acronym GeoSust), Contract No 22 SEE/30.06.2014.

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